

USING GEOSTATISTICAL METHODS TO QUANTIFY VARIATION IN LUNAR REGOLITH FOR RESOURCE EXPLORATION. J. Witchalls¹, A. Calzada-Diaz¹, and K. Hadler^{1,2}, ¹European Space Resources Innovation Centre (ESRIC), Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), 5 Av. des Hauts-Fourneaux, L-4362, Luxembourg (joe.witchalls@list.lu), ²University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg.

Introduction: The growing interest in the use of in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) on the lunar surface to support future missions first requires the resources themselves to be delineated and quantified. Upcoming resource-oriented missions will be primarily focused on the early stage of resource exploration: Surface sampling, with some subsurface sampling [1]. However, using this data to inform early resource models, follow-up subsurface sampling, and ISRU technology design requires an understanding of the trends in the lateral and vertical variation in the regolith to enable extrapolation and interpolation between samples. The large quantity of lunar samples (~382kg) [2] which have been brought to Earth and analysed offers a very useful building block to extract geostatistical trends from and inform future sampling methods. However, previous approaches to lunar exploration have been primarily science-oriented, often prioritising anomalies and interesting samples to distribute to PIs to study the geological history of the Moon. As a result, sample collection, preparation and analysis methods often differed between missions and samples, making it difficult to reliably compare samples. This includes pre-analysis sieving or coarse particle removal, sampling the core at different intervals and targeted rather than systematic sampling methods.

The objective of this study is to demonstrate how existing sample data can be standardized to extract geostatistical trends, which can be used to inform future sampling plans on the Moon.

Methods: Apollo missions 15, 16 and 17 were used for this investigation, as the coring methods resulted in much less sampling error than previous missions and the surface sample datasets are larger and more robust, as they had use of the Lunar Roving Vehicle. The properties analysed were particle size distribution, modal mineralogy and geochemistry. To make the cores directly comparable, all cores were standardised to 5m intervals using weighted averages. The particle size distributions (PSD) of surface regolith samples were also reconstructed using the Handbook of Lunar Soils [3] and Graf et al., 1993 [4], similarly to previous work [5], and correlated to the nearby core samples to help estimate the difference in fully reconstructed PSDs between the surface (0-5cm) and the subsurface (0-55cm) across 8 core samples. D20, D50 and D80 passing sizes were used to represent the PSD where necessary. These indicate the size below which a certain percentage of particles are finer (i.e. 20% of the particles are finer than the D20 size). These were

compared to the variance observed in the EAC-1A simulant, extracted on a sampling grid across the surface of the ESA/DLR LUNA facility in Cologne.

Kriging, the geostatistical method commonly used in mining for resource estimation, was also performed on the in-situ geochemistry and modal mineralogy datasets for the Apollo 15 – 17 missions as well as on remote sensing data covering the landing sites. The variograms produced were compared to understand the scales at which variation is occurring and help inform sample spacing and resolution of future surface and satellite missions.

Results and Conclusions: Across the cores, the data suggests that the difference in modal mineralogy and geochemistry between the surface and the bulk regolith (down to 55cm) is small enough that surface sampling methods can be reliably used during early-stage resource exploration to identify targets for more extensive subsurface sampling. The particle size distributions show a finer surface than subsurface in all but one of the holes, however when datasets cut to certain size fractions are used and extrapolated to a fully reconstructed PSD, the trend indicates that the % difference between the surface and subsurface is significantly larger than what was previously observed for the <1mm fraction, the fraction typically used for analysis.

Reconstructed Apollo regolith PSDs show significant differences from the <1mm fraction which is typically used for analysing the regolith and designing lunar simulants. The variance between the Apollo samples also increases as sample size decreases, unlike the EAC-1A simulant, suggesting the Fundamental Sampling Error may pose an issue when dealing with more accurate, reconstructed PSDs. Technology testing with simulants should therefore consider including the coarser fraction, >1mm, ideally >1cm, as this more accurately reflects the actual lunar regolith and the potential sampling error that may occur with a realistic PSD.

Early indications from the Kriging analysis of in-situ and remote sensing data show that ranges can be extracted from the variograms of both datasets and may be consistent across mineralogical datasets. This could be used to inform sample spacing for future missions to ensure that the eventual interpolation between samples is robust enough for preliminary resource estimations.

References: [1] Pirrone, S.R.M., Witchalls, J., Dillenburger, J. *et al.* (2025) *Space Sci Rev* 221, 111 (2025). [2] Heiken G, Vaniman D, French BM (1991) Lunar sourcebook: a user's guide to the

moon. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
[3] Morris, R.V., (1983) *Handbook of lunar soils*.
Lyndon B. Johnson Space Center. [4] Graf, J. C.
(1993). *Lunar soils grain size catalog* (Vol. 1265)
[5] Kovtun, R. N., Gruener, J. E., & Slabic, A.
(2024). In *55th Lunar and Planetary Science Conference (LPSC)*.